

Original article

PROFITABILITY AND RISKS OF FINANCIAL INVESTMENTS

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abstract

Knowledge of the essence and understanding of modern features of the financial market, the time value of cash resources is currently a necessary condition for long-term business planning and its success. Unlike countries with developed economies, countries with weak economies are characterized by weak and unstable currencies, high risks. At the same time, despite the relatively low interest income in developed countries, financial assets generate more.

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Introduction

In the global market, there is always fierce competition between countries for markets, income and investment. Governments and businesses, millions of people make consumer and investment decisions of a short-term and strategic nature, based on their own capabilities, the price and quality of goods, market conditions, risks and profitability of investments. [1]

The global financial market represents a set of various instruments, describes a simple circulation of national currencies moved from one country to another using various instruments, between industries, depending on the levels of profitability and risks characteristic of these industries and countries.

The pattern is that finance, finished goods, raw materials, labor resources are moving from countries with low prices to countries where prices are higher and risks are lower. From the point of view of financial expediency, this corresponds to the nature of capital, market laws and the choice of the individual. Investors tend to invest and move capital from low-income countries to countries where these indicators are higher and risks are lower.

Countries with developed market economies have market power, that is, the ability and ability to provide low risks, high incomes, influence world prices, terms of

sale and purchase, ensure the stability of their own currency, form supply and demand. These countries can offer the best price for assets, financial, raw materials, currency and human resources. At the same time, goods and services can be delivered to consumers and businesses under the best conditions from the price, quality, delivery and payment terms, guarantees, etc.

Unlike countries with developed economies, countries with weak economies are characterized by weak and unstable currencies, high risks. And, despite relatively low interest rates in developed countries, financial assets generate more income than investments with high returns in weak countries.

Currently, most of the world's markets, assets and resources are located in developed countries. These countries can divert the world's resources much more easily.

Analysis of the literature used

Finance as an economic category was considered by the Scottish economist, one of the founders of economic theory as a science, the founder of its classical school Adam Smith in his work "The Wealth of Nations" (1776). The theory of finance and its practical application, the use of finance theory to solve practical problems, the identification of those facts and important information needed by financial managers are widely presented by Richard Brayley (London Business School) and Stuart Myers (Massachusetts Institute of Technology). R. Kiyosaki, the author of the bestseller, the businessman's handbook "Rich Dad, Poor Dad", writes about the basics of financial education, the achievement of financial freedom.

Research methodology

To clearly display the time value of financial assets and the results of investing in total and dollar long-term assets, data comparison, methods of system analysis, forecasting, and scientific abstraction were used.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the modern features of the financial market, understanding the time value of monetary resources.

"The main reason that people are experiencing financial problems is that after spending years at school, they did not learn anything about what money is. As a result, people learn to work for money... but never learn how to make money work for themselves." [3] The author talks about the thinking of poor and rich people.

According to the theory of monetary circulation [2], high interest rates in one country can attract financial investments from other countries. In practice, this is partially true.

In developed countries, an increase in interest rates leads to the attraction of foreign exchange resources of other countries, a decrease in the level of currency devaluation.

Results

When making investment decisions, investors look not only at the interest rate of assets, but also at the exchange rate and their forecast for the future. And if the devaluation of the currency of a country with an unstable economy turns out to be higher than the interest rate in this country, then this does not increase the investment attractiveness of this country's investments, even with their higher profitability. With a weak currency and high returns on financial assets (for example, securities, deposits), it will still be more profitable for investors to invest in assets denominated in a strong currency, despite their lower returns.

Countries with strong economies can attract investment even with negative activity. In countries with unstable economies, inflationary and devaluation expectations of investors are high, and investors from countries with weak economies are ready to invest their resources not in the local market, where profitability may be high, but in assets of developed economies, even if their profitability is negative.

Consider the options for investing five thousand US dollars into a foreign currency account on the terms of 3 to 5 percent yield per year and a sum deposit at 24, 22 and 21 percent per annum. At the time of deposit placement, the exchange rate is 8500 soums per 1 dollar, that is, a sum deposit of 42 million 500 thousand soums. Deposits for a period of 5 years. Subject to sum deposits on terms of 21 percent per annum (1.75 percent per month), and in dollars at 3 percent per year (0.75 percent per month), a sum deposit (700 percent) seems 7 times more profitable.

Calculation of interest accrual

Table 1

years	Accrued interest, in soums			exchange rate	Value in US dollars		
	at 24%	at 22%	at 21%		at 24%	at 22%	at 21%
2019	10200000	9350000	8930000	8500	1200	1100	1050,6
2020	10200000	9350000	8930000	10200	1000	916,7	875,5
2021	10200000	9350000	8930000	12240	833,3	763,9	729,6
2022	10200000	9350000	8930000	14688	694,4	636,6	610
2023	10200000	9350000	8930000	17625,6	578,7	530,4	510
in total	51000000	46750000	44650000		4306,4	3947,6	3775,7

We assume an annual devaluation of the Uzbek soum to the dollar at the level of 20 let's compare the profitability of investments (Table 2).

Calculation of the profitability of sum deposits

Table 2

Indicators	Values
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Investment volume	dollars	5 000,0		
Dollar exchange rate at the time of purchase of total assets	soums	8500		
Investments in financial assets	soums	42500000,0		
Currency exchange rate at the time of repayment	soums	17625,6		
Annual currency devaluation	%	20		
Return on total assets	%	24	22	21
Total amount of accrued interest	dollars	4306,4	3947,6	3775,7
Repayment of sum assets – accrued interest	dollars	2893,5	2652,4	2533,25
Return on total investments	%	15,78	15,3	15,1

Consider the option of investing in dollar financial assets.

Investments in dollar financial assets

Table 3

Investment volume	dollars	5000,0	
Repayment of dollar assets	dollars	5000,0	
Return on assets	%	3,0	5,0
The total amount of accrued interest for 5 years	dollars	750,0	1250,0
Total income	dollars	5750,0	6250,0
Profitability	%	15	25

When comparing the total deposit at 21 percent per annum and the foreign currency with the condition of 3 percent, all other things being equal, there is practically no difference in the choice of investments.

More favorable conditions (22, 24 percent) give a slight advantage of total deposits. But an increase in the yield of a foreign currency deposit by only 2 percent increases the yield by 10 points. For long-term deposits, sum deposits lose their attractiveness with the current level of inflation.

Thus, for each specific offer, it is necessary to analyze risk factors, terms and conditions of total and currency financial assets.

Even with a high level of return on total assets, Uzbek investors are more likely to sell their assets, buy US dollars and invest them in dollar securities (for example, bonds) of countries with stable economies at a given level of currency devaluation. That is, if the level of currency devaluation exceeds the profitability of financial assets, it is unprofitable for investors to invest in total assets, they rather invest in assets denominated in strong currencies, usually in US dollars.

It is much harder for countries with weak economies to mobilize financial resources, because businesses and individuals tend to invest their foreign exchange resources in less risky assets and countries that provide relatively high incomes.

Conclusion

With a stable currency, the value of assets and income received in this currency become stable and predictable. The more stable the currency, the more investors invest in assets denominated in this currency, the demand for it increases.

Inflation and currency devaluation are beneficial to borrowers and, accordingly, unprofitable to creditors. The globalization of the financial sphere implies the creation of a world market and a currency system, when the role of the world currency is performed by currencies that are stable and in demand on the world market.

Countries with unstable economies need to take into account the patterns and experience of developed countries when forecasting economic policy based on the current conditions and capabilities of the country. Countries with strong economies are characterized by:

- formation of macroeconomic forecasts based on moderate economic growth rates;
- efficient use of domestic resources and the use of loans for the production of export-oriented and import-substituting goods and services;
- restriction of imports of consumer goods and services, except for socially significant ones;
- the use of adequate restrictions on current and capital currency transactions, taking into account the experience of developed countries.

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